

International Journal of Information Technology Convergence and Services (IJITCS)

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Scope & Topics

International Journal of Information Technology Convergence and Services (IJITCS) is a bi-monthly open access journal that publishes articles which contribute new results in all areas of Information Technology Convergence and services. The journal focuses on all technical and practical aspects of ITC & S. The goal of this journal is to bring together researchers and practitioners from academia and industry to focus on understanding Information Technology Convergence and services and establishing new collaborations in these areas. Authors are solicited to contribute to the journal by submitting articles that illustrate research results, projects, surveying works and industrial experiences that describe significant advances in the areas of Information Technology Convergence and services.

Topics of interest include, but are not limited to, the following:

- Advanced IT Bio/Medical Engineering
- Bioinformatics and applications
- Business and Information Systems
- Cloud computing
- Convergence in Information Technology Security
- Data Mining and Knowledge Discovery
- Digital convergence
- Electronic Commerce, Business and Management
- Grid and Cloud Computing
- Intelligent Robotics and Autonomous Agents
- Hardware and Software Design
- Health and Medical Informatics
- Hybrid information technology
- Intelligent communications and networks
- IT-based Convergence Technology and Service
- Multimedia convergence
- Smart Card and RFID Technologies
- Soft Computing and Intelligent Systems
- Social and Business Aspects of Convergence IT
- Ubiquitous Computing and Embedded Systems

Paper Submission

Authors are invited to submit papers for this journal through **Submission System**. Submissions must be original and should not have been published previously or be under consideration for publication while being evaluated for this Journal. For paper format download the template in this page Manuscript Template

Important Dates

- Submission Deadline : June 27, 2020**
- Notification : July 27, 2020**
- Final Manuscript Due : August 04, 2020**
- Publication Date : Determined by the Editor-in-Chief**

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